

A new subspecies of *Morimus verecundus* (Faldermann, 1836) from Bulgaria and a new subspecies of *Morimus asper* (Sulzer, 1776) from Greece (Coleoptera, Cerambycidae)

M.L. Danilevsky¹, D.Gradinarov² & O. Sivilov²

¹A.N. Severtzov Institute of Ecology and Evolution, Russian Academy of Sciences, Leninsky prospect 33, Moscow 119071 Russia

e-mail: danilevskym1@rambler.ru, danilevsky@cerambycidae.net

²Sofia University "St. Kliment Ohridski", Sofia, Bulgaria

e-mail: dgradinarov@abv.bg, osivilov@gmail.com

Key words: new species, taxonomy, Cerambycidae, Lamiinae, *Morimus*, Bulgaria, Greece.

Abstract: *Morimus verecundus bulgaricus* Danilevsky, **ssp. n.** is described from Black Sea coast in north-east Bulgaria (Balchik and Varna). *M. asper graecus* Danilevsky, **ssp. n.** is described from Greece (Peloponnesus: Chelmo Mt. and Taygetus Mts).

A new *Morimus* species was recently described from Slovakia: *M. gabzdili* Danilevsky, 2015. Now we can continue the study of European *Morimus* populations.

Morimus verecundus bulgaricus* Danilevsky, **ssp. n.*

Figs 1-2

Type locality: Bulgaria, Balchik, University Botanic garden, 43°24'13"N, 28°8'42"E, 34 m.

The new subspecies is rather close to the population of the nominative subspecies from Black Sea coast of Russia (Podhrebtovoe, 44°22'35.00"N, 38°57'47.00"E, 140m, 8.6.2010, M.Danilevsky leg. - 5 males and 4 females available) with dense pale pubescence on 4 elytral spots with sparse granulation. Similar specimens were collected in Krasnodar environs (park "Krasnyi Kut").

Antennae in males about 1.7-1.8. times longer than body, surpassing elytral apices by 5 apical joints (while in males of *M.v.verecundus* antennae usually more than 2 times longer than body surpassing elytral apices by 6 apical joints); antennae in females a little longer than body; 1st antennal joint is about as long as 5th in

M.L. Danilevsky, D. Gradinarov, O. Sivilov

males or about as long as 4th in females; 4th joint is rather longer than 5th, 3rd joint is the longest; prothorax in males about as long as basal width or about 1.1 times longer; in females - also about as long as basal width or a little shorter; lateral thoracic spines much shorter than in *M. verecundus* from Russia; scutellum strongly transverse without distinct posterior emargination; elytra in males 1.8-2.0 times longer than basal width, in females - 1.8-1.9 times; elytral granulation moderately dense, similar to the nominative subspecies; four large elytral spots can be densely covered with pale pubescence and partly devoid of granules; posterior elytral half with irregular areas of pale pubescence and sparse small granulation; body length in available males: 20-30 mm, body width (at elytral middle): 7-12mm; body length in available females: 24-31mm; body width: 9-12 mm.

In general new subspecies differs from *M.v.verecundus* by shorter antennae and shorter lateral thoracic spines. Further morphological comparison of two subspecies is rather desirable, but needs more materials.

Materials. Holotype, male, Bulgaria, Balchik, University Botanic garden, 43°24'13"N, 28°8'42"E, 34m, 14.6.2006, I.Iliev leg. - Zoological collection of Sofia University St. Kliment Ohridski, Faculty of Biology (BFUS); 4 paratypes; 1 male from same locality, 17.6.2013, I.Iliev leg. - collection of M.Danilevsky; 1 female, Bulgaria, Varna, University Botanic garden, 43°14'8"N, 28°0'8"E, 57m, I.Iliev leg. - Zoological collection of Sofia University St. Kliment Ohridski, Faculty of Biology (BFUS); 1 male and 1 female from same locality, 12.06.2008, 20.06.2013, I.Iliev leg. - collection of M.Danilevsky.

Remarks. Both known localities of the subspecies are situated in NE Bulgaria, at a distance up to two km from the Black Sea coast. At the inland territory of Bulgaria the genus *Morimus* is represented by *M. asper funereus* (Mulsant, 1863) (after Migliaccio et al., 2007). Additionally, *M. orientalis* Reitter, 1894 has been reported several times from SE Bulgaria (Bringmann, 1996; recent report by Georgiev et al., 2015). Further investigation is needed for clarification of distribution and biological features of the new subspecies.

Morimus asper graecus Danilevsky, ssp. n.
Figs 3-4

Type locality: Greece, Peloponnesus, Chelmos Mt. (about 37°58'26"N, 22°12'25"E).

The new subspecies does not look too much similar to the nominative subspecies *Morimus asper asper* from Italy (7 males and 4 females are available: BO, Casalecchio di Reno, G. & I. Zappi leg.; 2 similar males are available from Elba Island) because of wider body with very dense conjugated elytral punctation.

Antennae in males a little more than 2 times longer than body, surpassing elytral apices by 6 apical joints; antennae in females a little longer than body; 1st antennal joint distinctly shorter than 5th in males or a little longer in females; 4th joint is a little longer than 5th in males or rather longer in females, 3rd joint is the longest; prothorax in males about as long as basal width, or about 1.1 times shorter (in Italian *M. a. asper* prothorax is a little elongated); in females about 1.1 times shorter than basal width; lateral thoracic spines a little longer than in Italian *M. a. asper*; scutellum strongly transverse, without posterior emargination, while in Italian *M. a. asper* scutellum semicircular; elytra in males about 1.7 longer than basal width, in females - about 1.8 times; elytral granulation extremely dense, granules are often touching each other or conjugated (never in Italian *M. a. asper*); four large elytral spots are totally granulated and can be indistinct, or slightly pronounced because of recumbent black pubescence; posterior elytral half without areas of sparse granulation; body length in available males: 27-34 mm, body width (at elytral middle): 9-12mm; body length in available females: 32-38mm; body width: 12-13 mm.

New subspecies remarkably differs from Italian *M. a. asper* by wider body with wider prothorax in males and by very dense conjugating elytral granulations.

Materials. Holotype, male, Greece, Peloponnesus, Chelmos Mt. (about 37°58'26"N, 22°12'25"E), 21.6.1981 M. Slama leg. - MD; 4 paratypes; 2 males, 1 female, Greece, Peloponnesus, Taygetus Mts (about 36°57'14"N, 22°21'08"E), 18.6.1977, J. Hladil leg. - MD; 1 female, Greece, Peloponnesus, Taygetus, Artemisia (37°6'N, 22°13'50"E), 8-11.6.1980, Brodsky & Bily leg. - MD.

M.L. Danilevsky, D. Gradinarov, O. Sivilov

Remark. A single male available from mainland Greece (Parnassos Mt., 22.6.1977, M.&J. Hladolovi leg. - MD) also has conjugating elytral granulation and most probably belongs to the new subspecies.

Acknowledgements. We are very grateful to all colleagues who collected available materials.

REFERENCES

- Bringmann H.D. 1996. Die Morimus - und Acanthoderes - Arten Bulgariens (Col., Cerambycidae). - Entomologische nachrichten und berichte. 40: 237-239.
- Danilevsky M.L. 2015. A new species of the genus Morimus Brullé, 1832 (Coleoptera, Cerambycidae) from Central Europe. - Humanity space. International almanac. 4(2): 215-219.
- Georgiev G., Gjonov I., & Sakalian V. 2015. New Records of Longhorn Beetles (Coleoptera: Cerambycidae) in Strandzha Mountain. - Journal of the entomological research society. 17(2): 73-88.
- Migliaccio E., Georgiev G. & Gashtarov V. 2007. An annotated list of Bulgarian Cerambycids with special view on the rarest species and endemics (Coleoptera: Cerambycidae). - Lambillionea. 107(1), supplément 1: 1-78.

Figs 1-2. *Morimus verecundus bulgaricus* Danilevsky, **ssp. n.:**

1 - male, holotype, 2 - female, paratype, Bulgaria, Varna, University Botanic garden, 43°14'8"N, 28°0'8"E, 57 m, 12.6.2008, I.Iliev leg.

Figs 3-4. *Morimus asper graecus* Danilevsky, **ssp. n.:**

3 - male, holotype, 4 - female, paratype, Greece, Taygetos, Artemisia, 8-11.6.1980, Brodsky & Bily leg.

Received: 29.03.2016

Accepted: 30.03.2016